

An Analysis of the Strategic Business Processes of Karupalli: Challenges and Opportunities in the Bangladeshi Handicraft Sector

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Letter of Transmittal

25 August, 2017

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Subject: Submission of the Thesis paper.

Sir,

It is a great pleasure that I am going to complete my thesis paper on “**An Analysis of the Strategic Business Processes of Karupalli: Challenges and Opportunities in the Bangladeshi Handicraft Sector**”. I have worked both at the main office at “kawran Bazar” and in marketing department. On the basis of the report, I have tried to incorporate the real business process they follow. It will give a total overview of Karupalli’s whole business process. I have tried to include all the practical aspects of operation of them and a concept how it is going on under real situation.

My attempt is to relate the practical issues taught backed by your proper guidance. I have tried heart and soul to make the paper as comprehensive as possible. But there may be some mistakes due to various limitations. So I beg your kind consideration in this regard. I hope that you will approve the paper and it will meet your standards.

In this regard, special gratitude goes to you for forwarding your helping when I want to you.

Sincerely,

Md. Raihanul Islam

.....

MBA Roll - 540

Batch No: 18th

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STUDENT DECLARATION

I am Md. Raihanul, hereby declare that the presented report titled “**An Analysis of the Strategic Business Processes of Karupalli: Challenges and Opportunities in the Bangladeshi Handicraft Sector**” is uniquely prepared by me after collecting and analyzing all the valuable data on Online buying intention.

I also confirm that the report is only prepared to meet my academic requirement; not for any other purposes. It should not be used for the interest of any opposite party.

Sincerely,

Md. Raihanul Islam

.....

MBA Roll - 540

Batch No: 18th

Major: Marketing

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Supervisor's Certification

This is to certify that the thesis paper on “**An Analysis of the Strategic Business Processes of Karupalli: Challenges and Opportunities in the Bangladeshi Handicraft Sector**” has been submitted for the fulfillment of the degree of Masters of Business Administration (MBA) at Department of Marketing, Faculty of Business Studies, University of Dhaka by **Mr. Md. Raihanul Islam, his MBA ID is 540, session 2015-2016**. He has done his job according to my supervision and guidance.

He is permitted to submit the thesis paper

Best regards,

.....

Abureza M. Muzareba
Assistant Professor
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At first I would like to remember almighty Allah who has given me the opportunity to complete my report successfully as a partial requirement of MBA program.

I am grateful to my thesis supervisor honorable teacher Abureza Mohammad Muzareba, Assistant Professor, Department of Marketing, Faculty of Business Studies, who has guided me properly to prepare this report on the proposed topic. In the report proposal, he inserted necessary corrections and suggestions. Later on, I have completed my work based on those suggestions.

I would like to express my gratitude to the Karupalli authority because they provided me with great sources of information, adequate data and lastly helped me for the finished of this report successfully. Finally, I would like to thank each and every Staff of the different divisions for their kind assistance regarding the report. Without whom it would not possible for me to finish this difficult task, I got all necessary cooperation, advice from them to complete this task. I am very much thankful to Karupalli, its management, especially employees of Marketing & Sales for their cordial support to prepare this difficult study with important data and information.

Finally I want to express my heartfelt gratitude to all the colleagues of Karupalli and my friends those who support me by whatever means they had.

Md. Raihanul Islam

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Executive Summary

This report is the outcome of the thesis program ran for the past Ninety days placed at the Karupalli. The purpose of this study is to find out how Karupalli run their whole business process. So I had to gain the practical knowledge about the organization and face with the environment directly to understand the nature and types of strategy of the organization.

Strategic business analysis has become a crucial part for getting insights about the business process. A strategic analysis for a business is one of the most basic and useful tools for strategic business planning. In the discussion part some important business strategies are discussed like- training and development strategy, pricing strategies, marketing strategies, BRDB-Karupalli model, value chain process, SWOT Analysis, key success factors, Porter's five forces model and PESTLE Analysis. In this report Karupalli's whole business process, a survey on the online marketing effectiveness of Karupalli compared to its competitors is given with findings and Analysis. There are many problems found in the findings and analysis part that are facing by Karupalli because of various reasons. Those are also included here.

In the recommendation part the possible recommendations that can be used by Karupalli and that will ultimately will help to improve their current scenario. Finally, the whole report will help to understand the whole strategic business process that followed buy Karupalli and how to the current fashion houses competition.

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Introduction:

Handicrafts are mostly defined as items made by hand, often with the use of simple tools, and are generally artistic and traditional in nature. They are also object of utility and object of decoration. Some common types of handicrafts are Textile based handicrafts, Clay, Metal, Jewelry, Woodwork, Stone Craft, Glass and Ceramic. People have a distinctive sense of art. From the beginning of the civilization, they have created innumerable things as a blossom of this sense. Now, most of the handicrafts are produced, traded and exported by Karupalli, Karupponno Rangpur, Dhaka Trade, Kumudini, Aarong, Nipun Crafts, Creation and Pioneers. Along with those, there are many new enterprises. Market demand and competition are increasing. So to compete in this growing challenging market, organization needs effective and efficient value chain and innovation.

In this report I am trying to analyze the whole strategic business process of “Karupalli” by using various models and will find out their problems, ways of improvements with recommendations. A questionnaire survey will be conducted on “the Karupalli’s Online Marketing Effectiveness on Customer’s Behavior compared to their Competitors Online Marketing activities”.

Literature Review:

Strategic business analysis has become a crucial part for getting insights about the business process (Parry, 2002). It is defined (Ries & Trout, 2010) that a strategic analysis for a business is one of the most basic and useful tools for strategic business planning. Additionally, strategic business analysis is needed (Ries & Trout, 2010) to gain competitive market share, or how to build company's image (Parry, 2002). The core things in strategic business analysis are- strategy description, strategy evaluation, strategic issues, strategic recommendation. Currently, it is analyzed for the whole company, which helps to determine the impact on specific departments of the business. In the key success factors for the business, these factors encompass an organization's core attributes that must remain in the business, and will help to implement competitive strategy. Besides, technical requirements are also needed to build a competitive position. This analysis will help to determine the costs and forecast the profits got from the product in future financial years. The costs of developing a product are substantial and this analysis helps to eliminate inappropriate ideas and avoid unnecessary costs.

Besides, a marketing strategy (Ries & Trout, 2010) helps to create products and services with the best chances for making a profit. This is because marketing strategy starts with marketplace research, taking into consideration optimal target customer, what competitors are doing and what trends might be on the horizon. This information determines what customers' and clients' want what they're willing to pay and to differentiate the product or service from the competition. All marketing strategy is built on STP – Segmentation, Targeting and Positioning (Kotler & Keller, p.310). In the chapter of fundamental marketing concepts, trends, and tasks it says: “A marketer can rarely satisfy everyone in a market. Not everyone likes the same cereal, hotel room, restaurant, automobile, collage or movie. Therefore, marketers start by dividing up the market into segments” (Kotler & Keller, 2005, p.24).

Segmentation is often the key to develop a sustainable competitive advantage based on differentiation, low cost, or a focus strategy (Parry, 2002, p.49). It is difficult to identify segments, but needs to consider five, ten or more segmentation variables. These variables are needed to be evaluated on the basis of their ability to identify segments for which different

strategies pursued (Parry, 2002, p.51). Once the segments are defined, it is possible for the marketers to evaluate what segments presents the greatest opportunity for business and make an offer to target this specific segment. Secondly, it comes to target market. Target Marketing (Sbinfo, 2014) involves breaking a market into segments and then concentrating in the marketing efforts on one or a few key segments. It can be the key to attract new business and making business a successful one. The beauty of target marketing is that it makes the promotion, pricing and distribution of products or services easier and more cost-effective. It provides a focus to all of the marketing activities. Lastly, with positioning strategy, a company must capture a position in the prospect's mind. This is described in the book Positioning (Ries & Trout, 2010), who claims that the market place today is an over communicated society where there is too much of information communication its offer (Ries & Trout, 2006, p.6). This is the reason of needing positioning. Positioning helps to communicate the message of the market place in the over communicated society.

In marketing strategies, the marketing mix is a major part of any organization. Neil H. Borden (1964) defined about marketing mix as a "Mix of Ingredients- The four p's, of the marketing mix elements are product, place, promotion and price." Marketing mix, also known as the 4P's of Kotler (2005, p.19), describes the marketing tools and variables used by a company to pursue its marketing objectives. These four elements create the marketing mix which impacts the development of any organization's marketing strategies and tactics.

In other words, the "Marketing Mix" approach to marketing is a model used to assist in implementing marketing strategies. The marketing mix principles are based on controllable variables which can be used by companies to meet the changing needs of the target group. Typical controllable variables are product variety, quality, list price advertising and channels. The function on the model is useful helping companies to develop an optimal package (mix) of variables that will not only satisfy the needs of their customers within the target markets, but also simultaneously maximize the performance and profit of the company. Pricing is an important but difficult issue in this model, important because it is the only mix that generate a turnover for the company, all other P's in the model are connected to costs, and "Pricing is difficult because the various products have demand and cost interrelationship and are subject to different degrees of competition" Kotler (2005, p.387).

To develop a strategy, research about the business and the environment is very necessary. It is defined (Kimi Ziemski, 2008) that SWOT analysis, PORTER 5 force analysis , PESTLE analysis and other relevant models are needed to know the overall atmosphere of the business to take optimum strategic steps. SWOT analysis evaluates four elements of the business- strength, weakness, opportunities and threat (Albert Humphrey, 1964). It starts by defining the objective of the project or business activity and identifies the internal and external factors that are important for achieving that objective. Strengths and weaknesses are usually internal to the organization, while opportunities and threats are usually external.

The value chain is, according to the handbook for value chain research by Kaplinsky and Morris (2002) "The full range of activities which are required to bring a product or service from conceptions, through the different phases of production (involving a combination of

physical transformation and the input of various producer services), delivery to final consumers, and final disposer after use". Value chain allows the firm to understand which parts of its operations create value and which do not. The value chain analysis is based on Michael Porter's generic value chain model (Porter, 2001), developed in 1985 and used to explore Porter's model of competitive advantages through differentiation or cost leadership strategy. Besides, PESTLE analysis is needed to know the external environment of the business. It is a simple and widely used tool that helps to analyze the Political, Economic, Socio-Cultural, and Technological changes in business environment (Francis Aguilar, 1967).

Based on the report of Hoffman & Novak (1996), the Internet is so powerful that it can drastically modify the way businesses interact with their customers. A smashing example is the Tesco, well-known UK Retail shop, which shifted its market to the online marketing and as a result to that its sales increased up to 32% per year. Today, it is a challenge for organizations to know their customers while when consumers are introduced to new technologies their behaviour changes (Zinkhan and Watson 1998, p.6). A great amount of studies have examined online consumer behaviour. A recent research supports that it is very difficult to understand the online consumer behaviour as each day businesses and the marketing place is being transformed (Koufaris 2002).

So, to get insights about the business process, a quantitative research has been undertaken (Malhotra, et al., 2010) by creating a questionnaire. The effectiveness of Karupalli's online marketing activities on Consumer behavior has been tested with this questionnaire.

Objectives of the Study:

Broad Objective: The primary objective of the study is to analyze and explore to get insights about total strategic business conducting process and surveying on the Karupalli's online marketing effectiveness on customer behavior.

Specific Objective(s):

- 1) To identify opportunities to increase sustainable competitiveness of Karupalli.
- 2) To clarify problems, constraints, challenges and prospects to increase competitiveness by analyzing actual and potential sources in the process of business model.
- 3) To offer suggestions, if needed, based on the analytical results of the current study

Significance of the Study:

This study will help to find out the strategies and current scenario of Karupalli. It will be very beneficial to know strategic management of the organization and help to know how the overall business is handled in the business process. This study will also help to identify the advantages and pitfalls of the organization which will help to take initiatives for further improvements. Moreover, this study will provide recommendations on how to evaluate the performance of a certain business process.

Methodology of the Study:

1. Nature of the Study

A descriptive research strategy will be used to conduct for the study. A survey questionnaire has been developed based on measurement of various aspects of the business to describe the overall scenario of Karupalli. Basically, it is a 'quantitative Research' for knowing the overall of situation of Karupalli.

2. Data Collection Techniques

- 1. Questionnaire:** A structured questionnaire has been developed to ask the customers of Karupalli.
- 2. Observation:** I will work at the outlet of Karupalli which is located at Karwan Bazar and will Customers.
- 3. Secondary information:** Secondary information will be collected by reviewing websites, Journals and some other relevant documents.

3. Sources of Data Collection

- 1. Primary Source:** The primary information is gathered through informal interviews of the employees working over there under management level, their salesman who are directly involved with selling product. Other's necessary data will be collected through observation and questionnaire survey.
- 2. Secondary Source:** Secondary sources have also been used to collect information. Secondary sources include journals, website, brochure, annula reports etc.

4. Sample Size

For quantitative data collection, the sample size is 50. Fifty customers have been selected for questionnaire survey.

5. Scaling

Actually, a five point scale will be used for the study. At one extreme of the scale there is strongly agree or to agree to a great extent and at the other, is strongly disagree or to a very little extent. Each point on the scale carries a score. Response indicating the least favorable degree is given the least score (say 1) and most favorable is given the highest score (say 5). We will Strongly Agree=5, Agree=4, Undecided=3, Disagree=2, and Strongly Disagree=1 scaling for scoring.

6. Sampling Technique

In quantitative data collection a convenience sampling technique will be followed to collect information. As it is a quantitative study with limited resources, such technique is followed to select samples as by using it, samples are easy to recruit. This technique is considered easiest,

cheapest and least time. On the other hand convenience sampling method is used as I am unable to access wider population and they have only one outlet.

7. Data analysis

Data have been analyzed according to the objectives set for the study. Different graphs, tables, charts and others instruments are used to make presentable the research results.

Business Strategies & Model(s):

In every business, there needs an action plan or strategy by which an organization can achieve its goal. Karupalli is using various business strategies to keep effective connection with overall business process. Taking various business strategies are helping them to optimize the efficiency level and growth of the business. The following strategies will be analyzed here.

1. Training and Development Strategy
2. Pricing Strategies
3. Marketing Strategies
4. BRDB-Karupalli Model
5. Value Chain Process of Karupalli
6. SWOT Analysis of Karupalli
7. Key Success Factors of Karupalli
8. Porter's Five Forces Model of Karupalli
9. PESTLE Analysis on Karupalli

1. Training and Development Strategy:

Karupalli has been created for the poor people who can make a good living by selling their own products. So it is very crucial to choose people who will be undertaken in the training

process. Karupalli has their own strategies to train their selected persons. They have a project called PP which means “Project Plan.” The duration of this project plan ranges from 2 to 5 years. Number of persons in the training process and type of training are given in the project plan.

There are two strategies by which Karupalli gives training to the selected persons. Firstly, they work directly with JICA to train the individuals. As Karupalli works with JICA (Japan Overseas Cooperative volunteers) , it selects the areas for JICA based on the people’s income, circumstance of the villages, training prospect, growth opportunities of the village, climate and some other factors. There are two volunteers, come from Japan, train the individuals. One of them is junior expert and the other is senior expert. Senior expert gives training to the individuals. Within two or five years experts conduct their training programs. They set a goal about how many people they will train in one year and after considering the overall factors, they start the training process.

Secondly, Karupalli works with BRDB (Bangladesh Rural Development Board) but here, Karupalli doesn’t work directly with BRDB. BRDB has own training programs, which are not considered on the basis of Karupalli. Those training programs are for various part of Bangladesh. In accordance with the government, BRDB gives training to the various people of Bangladesh. Here, Karupalli gives a direction about which training programs are needed for the chosen trainees. It gives an outline of training programs that the industry wants and by which people can make their own products and sell them with a better profit.

Karupalli gives trainings on tailoring, boutiques, embroidery, machine embroidery, sewing etc. These trainings help trainees to develop their skills and make a good living by selling their own skills to different organization.

2. Pricing Strategies

Price is the only element in the marketing mix that produces revenue; all other elements represent costs. Price is also one of the most flexible marketing mix elements. Unlike product features, prices can be changed quickly.

A. Pricing Objectives:

Pricing objective of karupalli is to set optimum price to provide maximum service. As Karupalli has been established for rural people development, the objective of setting price will be based on development purpose of rural people. Some basic pricing objectives are:

1. Survival:

In order to keep pace with the intense competition, or meet the changing consumer wants prices are the key so Prices are lowered to ensure inventory turnover but price must cover variable costs & fixed costs.

2. Maximum sales growth:

If production & distribution costs fall, all marketing and promotional activities will be disrupted. On the other hand, increased production & low price discourages competition.

3. Maximum Product-Quality:

Karupalli provides its customers maximum quality product with minimum price. Firm sets the product pricing higher than competitors in order to make higher quality of the products. Karupalli collects the raw materials from the same suppliers as Aarong does. So while setting the price, it considers all the factors.

4. Rural people Development:

Karupalli works for rural people development .It sets reasonable price to quantify total cost by which the minimum profit will be spent on rural people training as it is a nonprofit organization.

5. Minimum profit: The objective of price setting is to achieve minimum profit by providing maximum quality product.

B. General Pricing Strategies Used by Karupalli:

There are huge amount of products in Karupalli which cover more than 100 product lines. So, new product pricing strategy is needed for every new product line.,

It is selling traditional arts and handicrafts made from the rural parts of the country. At present it is an established business accounts for customer differences and changing situation. That's why price adjustment strategies are specially needed for this organization.

C. Price Adjustment Strategies:

1. Discount and Allowance Pricing

Karupalli reduces prices to reward customer's responses such as paying early or promoting the product. Karupalli reduces price on purchase during a particular period. For example: In "Pahela Baishakh" Karupalli provides discount.

2. Discount Card:

If customers purchase 20 products costing 200 BDT, Karupalli provides through its discount card.

3. Seasonal Discount:

When the customers purchase product out of season, Karupalli provides them seasonal discount. For example: warm-wear in June-July, purchasing shawl out of season like after or before winter season, stated amount of discount is provided.

4. Segmented Pricing:

Karupalli adjusts prices in order to allow for differences in customers, products, or location. According to two or more criteria price is set.

1. Age,
2. Gender,
3. Social class,
4. Personality,
5. Life style,

6. Psychological Pricing:

In order to handle customers psychologically or to create reference pricing, Karupalli adjusts prices. For example; if any company wants to be the *low-cost leader*, it must be priced lower than its competitor. On the other hand, if anyone wants to signal high quality, it should price higher than most of its competitor. Sometimes consumers perceive higher priced product as having higher quality. That's why as a quality signal, Karupalli sets price higher as a higher quality product.

7. Promotional Pricing:

Sometimes Karupalli temporarily reduces price in order to increase short run sales. Karupalli prices their products below list price to create buying excitement and urgency. For example:

8. Dynamic Pricing:

Karupalli continually adjusts prices to meet the characteristics and needs of individual customers and situations. Specially to meet the customized demand of segmented market, Karupalli follows dynamic pricing.

4. Marketing Strategies:

In this section Karupallis whole marketing strategies including segmentation, targeting, positioning are describing below.

Segmentation, Targeting, Positioning

A. Segmentation:

Karupalli segments their market on the basis of some variables like- age, gender, social class, personality, life style, occupation, use of occasion, benefits, user status etc.

Initially, they divide the market in to three parts like- upper class, middle class and lower class. They also divide the market on the basis of age like- 20-40 years, 40+ years. Gender is another factor here because both male and female have different preferences to their products. But for handicraft products, female are more interested than male. On the other hand, some people like classic products and others like trendy products. But they are focusing on both classic products and fashionable products. They also think about occupation of the customers. So, they divide it into few parts like- job holders, business persons, students. There are lots of occasions like- Pahela Baishakh, Eid-ul-Fitr, Puja, International mother language day, Valentine's Day, Victory day etc. Karupalli also thinks about these occasions at the time of segmentation. They also segment their market on the basis of user benefits because users want benefits. Without giving them benefits, they will not come to buy from Karupalli. They think about price, products quality, availability etc. Finally, they think about the user status. They divide their users into few parts like- fixed customer, regular customer, new customer etc.

B. Targeting:

Karupalli targets one segment on the basis of selected variables. Their target market is 40+ years including both male and female. Mainly, 60% of their customers are female and 40% of their customers are male. As their 90% sales come from middle-class, they always produce their products for the middle class people. They target the people who are over 40 years because they find young people are not much interested in handicrafts and aged people are more interested in it.

C. Positioning:

1. Premium-Price Strategy

Karupalli prices its products or services in an average range to create a perceived value. Consumers wonder why a particular company is able to sell its product for more or why its fellow consumers are willing to pay more for the product. In the end, it makes them believe that the higher-priced product or service is worth more. Karupalli produces premium quality product with unique features comparatively reasonable price than its competitors.

2. Image Differentiation Strategy

Being an oldest handicraft brand of Bangladesh, Karupalli certainly desires its presence in any mass media. As Karupalli's market is defined geographically, it is not very efficient to go for those mass media that have a significant coverage beyond Karupalli's geographic

market comparing with the cost and benefits. Billboards appeared to meet both the criteria wonderfully. Billboard is a “one to many” type of communication media with a control over the geographic reach through photo-shoot. There are two types of photo shoots for Karupalli’ promotion.

1. Commercial Photography
2. Thematic Photography

Since all the customers come to Karupalli for making purchases, marketing communication with impressive display boards are installed. The ythink premium price is also working as an image differentiation for them. They said “ When we increased the price of our products we found that the products were getting sold easily”. Though high price is not good for all the time. It can be a negative side for them.

3. Channel Differentiation Strategy

Karupalli uses selected press media as another channel of communication. Since Karupalli is a traditional brand, placing advertisements on magazines & fashion supplements to be more effective in reaching the target customers. Considering facebook as a very popular social networking media, the billboard impressions are uploaded on facebook. Karupalli’ Page and all the members are notified about it. Next, Karupalli’s shopping bag is a very efficient channel to reach out to the customers intimately. Therefore, a new shopping bag has been introduced incorporating the essence of the new brand image.

4. Traditional Essence Differentiation Strategy:

Karupalli has a traditional essence of their product. As handicraft business is connected with us for a long period of time, Karupalli always wants to give traditional touch in their products showing elegance of choice.

Marketing Mix of “Karupalli:

The controllable tools of Karupalli are not enriched and they have lots of ways to improve the 4Ps. Here is given below-

1. Product:

Their main product was handicraft. But after few years of establishment they understood that only handicraft will not enough to get profit to run “Karupalli”. Then they also found that their main competitor Aarong was not only selling handicraft products but also selling apparels and foods. So, “Karupalli” started to sell apparels and most of their apparels are

made by “karupalli” but they collect “Jamdani” from producers. They always think about the quality of products. They have three major classes of products. They continuously change their products.

2. Price:

In a word, their price is high and quite similar with Aarong because they always try to maintain the quality and use the best material for their products. But they are planning to reduce their products price to attract more customers. Their pricing strategy is given below-

a. Handicraft Products Pricing: For handicraft products they keep approximately 40-50% mark-up on purchase price with out including operation costs. More specifically-

- I. Only for Nakshi Kantha they keep around 10% mark up.
- II. For customized products their markup amount is around 50%.

They can increase their mark up more than this but it will increase their rate of unsold products. As their handicraft suppliers are decreasing day by day, they cannot collect modern handicraft products. As a result their sell is decreasing and they are reducing their mark up on handicraft products.

b. Apparel Products pricing: For apparel products, they keep 45-50% mark up on purchase price with out including operation costs. More specifically-

- I. For common products their markup is 20-30%.
- II. For own produced products their markup is 40-100%.

Their price is high and similar to Aarong. But they get most of the sales from apperals. Product quality is the main reason of increasing price. They started selling apparel products as a back up of handicraft products but it is now main source of income.

c. Food products pricing: Actually, they collect foods from various sources and those prices are fixed by the producers. So, they get a little amount of profit and that amount is not fixed

Payment process: For payment system, they devide it in to two parts. One is for customers and other is for suppliers. The system of payment are-

1. When they sell their products they take 100% payment through cash or credit card/ debit card. They don't allow customers to purchase on debt.
2. When they purchase products from suppliers they take 100% payment through check.

3. Place:

They have only one sales centre and that is situated at 5 Karwan bazar, Dhaka. As they have only one sales center, they can't cover whole city. They had another sales center at Gulshan but for internal problems that sales center was sold.

4. Promotion:

For promotional activities they use-

1. Advertisement:

They provide advertisements at various fashion magazines like- Shaptahik 2000, Anondolok. They also provide Leaflet to make people aware about “Karupalli” and various discounts.

2. Sales Promotion:

They provide a fixed discount from 1st March to 13th April every year. The main objective of this discount is to sell all the unsold previous years products. At the time of Eid-ul-Fitr they participate at various dress competitions at Shaptahik 2000, Anondolok and Mirror. They also provide staff promotion. As a result, stuffs are more encouraged to buy from Karupalli.

3. Direct Marketing:

They contact with foreign buyers through email. That’s why many foreign buyers come to buy products from Karupalli. Their foreign buyers mainly come from Japan, Thailand etc.

4. Social Media Marketing:

In 2014 they opened their facebook page and started social media marketing. As a result, they are getting customers from online and they can also inform their customers about their new products, discounts and offerings. It’s a low cost but high return marketing technique of Karupalli.

5. Inbound Marketing:

As a member of Yellow page, Karupalli also get buyers directly from it. They are also the member of “Bangla Craft”, “Akota Forum”. So, those organizations are promoting Karupalli. They also provide support to Karupalli as a member of those organizations.

6. Newsletter: Japanese buyers know from Japan International Cooperative Agency’s newsletter about Karupalli. JICA supports Karupalli to help its handicraft producer’s economic development. In their newsletter write articles on Karupalli and its handicraft producers. That attracts Japanese come in Bangladesh and buys from Karupalli.

7. Third party endorsement: Export Promotion Bureau refers karupalli when any foreign buyers come to buy handicraft products in Bangladesh. As it is a government organization, Export Promotion Bureau gives preference to karupalli when any buyer comes to them.

8. Word of Mouth: Most of their customers come from word of mouth. So, they dont have to expend too much on advertising. Word of mouth is working here because their product quality is better than most of its competitors and the price is reasonable.

4. Bangladesh Rural Development Board (BRDB)-Karupalli Model:

BRDB-Karupalli model is for poverty alleviation and empowerment of the poor, especially women. Key features of the BRDB-Karupalli development model include:

1. Empowering Rural women:

Mainly, Karupalli is focusing on rural women and giving training for income-generating activities that enabled them to take charge of their lives and make improvements for themselves, their families and their communities.

2 Significant Differences:

The values of empowering people create a significant difference in the society. People who don't know about income generating activities are earning their livelihood now. The social impact of overall development is helping to reduce poverty and have a better growth of economy.

3 Projects Plan & Long-Term Sustainability:

In addition to BRDB's core programs, it also runs commercially operated, project plans which are strategically linked to its development programs. These project plans form crucial value chain linkages to increase productivity of assets and labor to reduce risk for the poor. The projects also help to make the organization increasingly self-sustaining

5. Value Chain Process of Karupalli:

1. Planning: Karupalli has no formal planning and forecasting. Planning depends according to decisions of top officials. For forecasting purpose, they generally depend on their experience and past year record to determine the procurement and production. Sometimes they prepare occasion based plan, specially for Eid-ul-Fitr and Pahela Baishakh.

2. Sourcing: Karupalli has large pool of sources to meets it supply. As the demand requires suppliers come up with raw materials and goods. Then it creates a product which we can use.

3. Production: Karupalli has a workshop in their organization building. Without this, Karupalli depends on the members of the co-operatives of BRDB.

4. Delivering: Karupalli doesn't have own transportation system. Suppliers or relevant parties have to send the raw materials or finished product with their own costs. Karupalli bears the cost after delivery has been done.

6. **Logistics:** Karupalli has top level management plans, supportive relation to their consumers and control of all other factors that have an impact on the supply chain.

7. SWOT Analysis of Karupalli:

SWOT analysis will help to identify Karupalli's whole business strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. So, in this section the organizations SWOT analysis is describing below:

a. Strengths:

1. Quality Products:

Karupalli gives quality products to its customers. The aesthetic products make customer satisfied and it continues to mesmerize the customers to have handicraft products in their lifestyle.

2. Reasonable Price:

Among all the competitors including Aarong, K-Kraft, Kumudini and others, Karupalli estimates a reasonable price for its customers. Though the cost of the materials is high, they always think about the market and the objective of establishing Karupalli. Because profit isn't the only thing they want from customers. There is a social purpose of capturing the profit to make better living of underprivileged people.

3. Diversified Products:

Currently, Karupalli is not only selling handicraft products but also selling garment products, foods and herbal products. Those product classes contain hundreds of product lines. Diversified products bring not only native customers but also foreign customers especially from Japan.

4. Sustaining Handicraft Products:

There are few organizations in Bangladesh, which are nourishing the handicraft market. Some people love to buy and use handicraft product because of the inherent difference in it. Though machines make the works easy but those can never cease the beauty of handicraft products.

5. Association with BRDB:

Karupalli gets various monetary and non-monetary benefits by Bangladesh Rural Development Board. BRDB's continuous contribution helps Karupalli to keep the product price stable in case of future crisis.

6. One-stop Shopping:

Customers can find huge amount of products in Karupalli. So, they can buy variety of products in one place. It saves both time and costs for the customer.

b. Weakness:

1. Lack of Advertising:

There is not rigorous advertisement compared with other competitors. Advertisements are not modified, modernized, updated which catch the customers' attention. Target market of advertising is not properly specified.

2. Business Location:

Karupalli's outlet is not in favorable place where customers can easily reach to it. Sometimes customers have to face hardship to look for the outlet.

3. Demand-Supply Gap:

There is a supply demand gap in Karupalli's product. Demand-supply gap is seen for various internal issues like delay of supplied raw materials, rejected products, quality issues and others.

C. Opportunities:

1. Opening new outlets:

There are opportunities where it can open new outlets. New outlets will help them to get more customers and increase growth of the business. If new outlets are properly located, there will be more reachable customers.

2. Direct online selling:

Karupalli is using third party website to sell their products whereas its competitors have own websites to sell products online. As online selling is becoming popular in our country, there is an opportunity to sell there through online.

4. Making smooth business process

As there are disorders in the flow of business, they can rectify the business process. It ranges from supplier to production and production to ultimate consumer.

5. New product lines:

Karupalli can introduce new product lines which actually match the needs of current market. If new product lines are properly identified, they can make huge profit from those product lines.

D. Threats:

1. Similar products:

Similar products are produced with more improved quality materials and aesthetic designs. If these products are used continuously, the market will be reduced for Karupalli. Besides, it will be a problem for keeping profit margin and business growth.

2. Security

Security of data, both online and offline has become a crucial issue in this time. Once data security has been lost, it costs millions for the business.

8. Key Success Factors of Karupalli

In Karupalli strategic plan, it carefully creates a vision of its future and the strategies needed to get there. From Karupalli's point of view, there are 4 critical factors that can ensure its strategic plans successful implementation.

a. Engagement

As strategic planning is a process, a key element in the process is the engagement of all levels of staff throughout the organization. Staff engagement generates additional input and helps build their commitment to the end plan. It is essential to involve employees in the planning of strategy and direction for the organization. Employee's input will provide insight into issues, challenges, concerns, and opportunities.

B. Communication

Strategic Planning processes are successful when communication among the stakeholders is properly managed. It starts off with a communication to all levels of employees informing them that a strategic planning process will be undertaken. It includes how they will be

involved in this process. This is the bottom up communication. Employees will provide input to the strategic planning process through feedback surveys, focus groups, meetings, etc. regarding their ideas for organizational direction, etc. It is followed by the top down communication. At Karupalli, Senior management would share the strategic plan with employees. They communicate to all employees how their engagement will help ensure success in the execution of these strategies.

C. Innovation

Karupalli believes in innovation of new products or deliver a new service. Recently, Karupalli has been affiliated with party website for increasing its sale. They also start to sell product through facebook.

D. Project management

Once the strategic plan is built, there are two critical elements related to project management. One is to identify the projects that are required to ensure success in the execution of each strategy. Another is to develop a prioritization of all these projects to ensure the high priority to ensure success. This requires a high involvement and commitment on the part of employees to spend the time required on the projects. Karupalli follows the high level of involvement of employees that they understand the strategic plan. It increases their level of commitment to ensure the successful execution because they understand how their work helps the organization to realize some or all of the key strategies.

9. Porter's Five Model of Karupalli

a. The Power of Supplier

The power of supplier is an assessment of how easy it is for suppliers to drive up prices. This is driven by the: number of suppliers of each essential input; uniqueness of their product or service; relative size and strength of the supplier; and cost of switching from one supplier to another. The bargaining power at karupalli is low because it determines the price of the product for the supplier.

b. The Power of Buyer

The power of buyer is an assessment of how easy it is for buyers to drive prices down. This is driven by the number of buyers in the market; importance of each individual buyer to the organization; and cost to the buyer of switching from one supplier to another. If a business has just a few powerful buyers, they are often able to dictate terms. In handicraft based retail industry, Karupalli has strong potential buyers so they may reduce their switching cost as well as increase the buyers' value.

c. Rivalry Among Competitors

Here, the main driver is the number and capability of competitors in the market. Rivalry among existing competitors takes many familiar forms, including price discounting, new product improvement, advertising campaigns, and service improvements, reduce market attractiveness. Karupalli follows the differentiated market strategy for different segmented customer. So its status in competitive rivalry is moderate compared with Aarong, Deshi Dosh, K-Kraft etc.

d. The Threat of Substitutes

Where close substitute products exist in a market, it increases the likelihood of customers switching to alternatives in response to price increases. This reduces both the power of suppliers and the attractiveness of the market. As there are huge substitute products of Karupalli, the threat of substitutes is high.

e. Threat of Entry

Profitable markets attract new entrants, which erodes profitability. Unless incumbents have strong and durable barriers to entry, for example, patents, economies of scale, capital requirements or government policies, profit will be declined in a competitive rate. Handicraft based lifestyle retail industry encourages new entry but Karupalli doesn't create high entry barriers through its high level of quality and brand value. so it has low threats on new entrance.

10. PESTLE Analysis on Karupalli

A PESTLE analysis is a framework or tool used by marketers to analyze and monitor the macro-environmental (external marketing environment) factors that have an impact on an organization. The result of which is used to identify threats and weaknesses which is used in a SWOT analysis.

A. Political Factors

These are all about how and to what degree a government intervenes in the economy. This can include – government policy, political stability or instability in overseas markets, foreign trade policy, tax policy, labor law, environmental law, trade restrictions and so on.

It is clear from the list above that political factors often have an impact on organizations and how they do business. According to political agreement of Bangladesh government Karupalli is now exporting their product in Japan through JAICA. As Karupalli is a government organization, political instability matters a lot. Lots of problems happen at the time of political strike. Due to government intervention, the organization lags behind in business activities.

B. Economic Factors

Economic factors have a significant impact on how an organization does business and also how profitable they are. Factors include – economic growth, interest rates, exchange rates,

inflation, disposable income of consumers and businesses and so on. These factors can be further broken down into macro-economic and micro-economic factors. Macro-economic factors deal with the management of demand in any given economy. Governments use interest rate control, taxation policy and government expenditure as their main mechanisms they use for this. Karupalli concentrates on economic factors and they ask customer for tax through Vat with the actual price of the product. Micro-economic factors are all about the way people spend their incomes. This has a large impact on B2C organizations in particular.

C. Social Factors

Social factors are the areas that involve the shared belief and attitudes of the population. These factors include – population growth, age distribution, culture, fashion, style, attitudes and so on. These factors are of particular interest as they have a direct effect on how marketers understand customers and what drives them. Karupalli follows the social factors and determines its target customer and marketing strategies.

D. Technological Factors

It is known that how fast the technological landscape changes and how this impacts the way we market our products. Karupalli has online shopping system for distributing their product to the target customer. It follows social media as well as electronic media for communication promotional activities.

E. Legal Factors

Legal factors including - health and safety, equal opportunities, advertising standards, consumer rights and laws, product labeling and product safety are followed by Karupalli. It is clear that companies need to know the legal ways to trade successfully. If an organization trades globally, this becomes a very tricky area to get right as each country has its own set of rules and regulations.

F. Environmental Factors

Karupalli considers environmental factors important due to the increasing scarcity of raw materials, pollution, wastage, and so on. These are just some of the issues marketers are facing within this factor. Karupalli believes in environment friendly products which won't cost harm to the environment. There are enormous wastages which are thrown to river banks or some place that cost severe damage the life-cycle of all species. So, Karupalli always tries to modify its production system for keeping sustainable environment for everyone.

Report Findings and Analysis:

1. Unskilled Labor and No Performance Appraisal System

Labor's are the power of any organization. Karupalli is suffering from lack of adequate labors. Every govt. Organization is facing this problem. They believe that there is a huge lacking of skillful labors. They are not getting training and they perform their daily activities without any liabilities to the organization. On the other hand, if employees or workers are not awarded, they will not work efficiently for the company. Karupalli don't have any performance appraisal system for the employees. Besides this there is no punishment for avoiding works.

Most of labors cannot work as karupalli wants. Only few workers give excellent effort and dedication. But only a few workers cannot make overall progress in business. Most of labors need to be skillful to improve business. Because of inadequate training, there is a problem of efficient employees in Karupalli. Consequently, employees cannot work in proper manner. As a govt. organization they don't have to give any feedback to the authority. Another thing is if any employee does better work he/ she dhon't get any reward or don't get punishment for mistake. Employees have to be awarded for their dedication for the job so that they will work with commitment for their organizations. On the other hand, punishment for avoiding works can improve their performance. Because it will make them aware about their daily tasks.

2. Decision making process

Every organization has to face a situation that they will have to take instant decision for any occasion or on the basis of market situation. Most of the cases we found it in private organization that they can take instant decisions because they have that decision making power from top to mid level. But in case of Karupally it is not possible to take decision instantly at the crucial moment without the permission of higher authority.

As Karupalli is a government organization, every single decision has been taken from top position officials. But officials are not concerned with immediate need of the decisions.

Hence, it is seen that, many consignments are lost or Karupali incurs huge loss for delay of decisions. They even can't take decision as well as initiatives for any occasion like Eid, Puja etc.

3. Manual process rather than automation

Manual activities are time consuming. So, many organizations are started using automation software's to make their work easy. In Karupalli most of the job is done here with manual procedures. Automatic system or machine is not used for the business. As a result they have to take huge time for official activities.

Without automatic process, organization lags behind the competition. Manual work is time consuming and less productive. Automation is needed for overall business growth. There are lots of stakeholders working with Karupalli. They believe that the information is not managed properly. As a government organization, they have lack in using automatic system. But the authority said they will start using automatic software very soon.

4. Planning & Implementation process

To get success in business planning is one of the most important parts. If planning is done properly it will be easy to implement. In case of Karupalli there are various measures taken by them but there is no proper planning for running the whole business process. They just take plan but don't bother for implement it.

Because of lack of proper planning most of their projects got in to dump. Besides, there is lack of alternative plans for which changes in plans creates problems in business process. One of the manager said if they take any good plan the higher authority most of the times don't give permission to implement it. So, they are frustrated and not interested to take these kinds of initiatives.

5. Decentralized Production

Centralized production reduces the cost of production. So, Products are produced in decentralized approach at karupalli. They collect products from various suppliers and also produce products at different places. They collect 65% of their products from suppliers and most of those are apparels, foods and beauty care products.

Decentralization in production waste both time and money. Besides, quality becomes a problem as products are not made with proper supervision. So, sometimes products are rejected because of quality problem. When decentralization process is long it takes lots of time to reach the products to outlets. On the other hand, they said they are trying to reduce cost by decentralizing production.

6. Lack of Parking Space

Parking space is a necessary part of a sales centre. When customers visit any shopping mall they also want to get some facilities like parking, food etc. But unfortunately there is lack of parking space for the customers.

As there is not have enough parking spaces for Karuplalli's customers it becomes a problem when a customer comes to Karupalli and he cannot find parking space. Eventually, they leave when they suffer from this sort of problem. Another thing is the road is quite narrow. So, customers don't feel comfortable to come with their private car to do shopping at karupalli.

7. Low Budget for running the business

As a government organization, they have low budget to meet the expense. On the other hand the salary and other benefits for sales stuff is comparatively low at karupalli. Sometimes it is seen inadequate supply of raw materials to produce their products on time.

As they don't have proper forecasting of their products there is congruence in forecasting of the products. It doesn't match the demand side with the supply of the product. Sometimes the budget is not properly utilized by the organization. Low budget hampers the process of marketing activities. They only focus on free marketing activities to reduce costs. As a result they are losing a huge amount of potential customers. On the other hand, Sales personnel don't work properly for the organization. Sales personnel who are directly connected with the customers need to be nourished properly. With proper appearance to the customers, they can bring profits from the business.

8. The number of female customers are high at Karupalli and their attitude towards the survey

On the above chart, the percentage of the Female customer is 77% and the Male customer percentage is only 23 percent. On the other hand, Home makers were unwilling to attend the survey. They tried to avoid it.

Home makers might be worried about giving information about them. Their facial expression and behaviors showed they are worried about the survey. Around 77% of the customers are not female because most of the karupalli's products are female apparels, handy craft products. As females are more interested in handy craft products the female customers rate will be high we can predict it. So, Karupalli mainly target the female segment of their customers.

9. Regular visitor of Karupalli's website and Facebook page

On the above chart, the percentage of Karupalli's Facebook page regular visitor is only 16% on the other had 84% of the customer never visited Karupalli's Facebook page. The percentage of Karupalli's website regular visitor is only 1% on the other hand 99% of the customer never visited Karupalli's page.

Both the Karupalli's facebook page and websites regular visitor rate is low because they don't do much promotional activities and their website doesn't have much information for customers. As a result their facebook sales rate is too low.

10. Payment procedure and product selling rate at karupalli and its competitions facebook page/ website

The payment procedure at facebook page is Bkash. They don't support any other payment procedure. Karupalli's competitors support not only Bkash but also other virtual cards for payment.

On the above chart, 3% of the Customers buy from Karupalli's facebook and 97% of the customers don't buy from their facebook page.

As they don't support another payment methods except Bkash, customers are not much interested to buy from Karupalli's facebook page. They are always looking for the convenient online purchase system. Karupalli only supports Bkash but its competitors are providing customers without cash and virtual card payment system. As a result customers feel conformable shopping at karupalli's competitor's website.

11. Karupalli's facebook promotional activities influence customers to purchase from them or not

On the above chart, 94% customers strongly disagreed, 4% disagreed, 1% agreed and 1% strongly agreed that Karupalli's facebook promotions influence to purchase from them.

It means customers don't see the facebook advertisements of Karupalli as they don't do much facebook advertising. Ultimately their online promotional activities don't influence much the customers to purchase their products. But their competitors are doing huge online promotional activities and influencing their customers to buy their products.

12. Customers opinion about Karupalli's E-commerce site launching

On the above chart, 71% customers strongly agreed, 15% agreed, 11% were neutral and 3% were strongly disagreed that Karupalli should turn their website to an E-commerce site.

Most of the customers said they want karupalli should launch their ecommerce site. Because it would be more convenient for them. Now a days, customers want to see the products by staying at home and buy from home and save their time. So, if Karupalli launch their ecommerce website it will be as profitable for them.

Recommendation:

1. Modernization

Most of the work in Karupalli is manual. As a government organization, it doesn't develop as much as the other competitors. Modernizing the overall business process will help the organization to grow the business rapidly.

2. Early payment

Payment should be paid as early as possible. Karupalli wastes a lot of time in paying wage of the employees. Late payments will frustrate the workers and eventually, it will hamper the work of production. Employees' attitude may be whimsical and organization's growth will be decreased.

3. Centralized Database

There is no centralized database system in karupalli. Data can be classified in the database software so that officials can use it when they need them. There are top-officials recruited by government who can also use any time for optimum decision making.

4. Ecommerce Site

Now, most of businesses has ecommerce website to sell products online. People can buy their products by visa card, master card or Bikash. If the site is properly maintained with effective communication, customers will come to buy their products from their site.

5. Online merchandizing records

Various organizations now keep their records by using online merchandizing software. This software is used to match the demands with supply of the products. Besides, they can use it for forecasting about what amount of stock should be kept for each product.

6. Commission in Sales

Salary isn't the only thing that the salesperson will motivate. They should be given commission according to sales target. If there is competition in sales among the salesperson, it will help business to capture extra profit.

7. Fashion Competition

Karupalli has been working quite a long time. So, branding is must for their business growth. Fashion competition can create a brand value for Karupalli. People from home and abroad will know the brand through the competition. Besides, there is an allusion in magazine or newspaper because of this competition.

8. Traditional Festival

In handicraft festival of our country, Karupalli can promote its variety of products to business customer from both home and abroad. It's a great opportunity to draw the attention of foreign customers.

9. Hiring Local Designer

Designs of Karupalli are create by Japanese designers. But in the competitive environment, there is also need of native designers. As local persons are much knowledgeable about the culture, taste, value, tradition, style and fashion of our country, native designers can be hired to work with the Japanese designers.

10. Conducting Research

Research can also be conducted to know what the current choice of the people is or what type of variety they want from Karupalli, which things need modification, by which products customers are biased. Conducting research will help the business to take suitable decisions.

11. Creative Advertising

Promotional activities can be taken by using facebook page, newspapers, magazines, and social networking websites. They can also use the billboards to have more awareness about their organization and products

12. More Active Participation in Social Media

Karupalli isn't much active in social media whereas other business organizations are much concentrated with it. People are using the social networking than ever before. So, there is a

good opportunity to reach the target consumer. They can also set the target in the social networking sites about which people they want to reach, their age, interest and so on.

13. Foreign Specialized Training

Employees can be trained in foreign countries so that they can add new values to products and services of Karupalli. Employees who are giving full dedication to Karupalli should be trained in foreign country. It will broaden their outlook of work and create an absolute vision for the organization.

Conclusion

Karupalli is doing their business quite a long time. The past 30 years of experience gives them various insights about the market. Currently, there are major changes in communication, promotion and technology. It is high time to use utilize the newer equipments in the industry. Though it is a government organization, it is high time to take necessary measures to save the organization and the connected projects of BRDB. If the overall situation is developed, people, society, economy will get benefit from it.

QUESTIONNAIRE

“ A survey on the Karupalli’s Online Marketing Effectiveness on Customer’s Behavior compared to their Competitors Online Marketing activities”

Name: _____

Gender: 1. Male female

Please mark the following questions answer

No.	Question	Yes	No			
1.	I regularly visit (□□□□□□□□) Karupalli’s Website	Yes	No			
2.	I am a Facebook user) □□□□□□□□□□)	Yes	No			
3.	I regularly watch) □□□□) Karupalli’s Facebook advertisements	Yes	No			
4.	I regularly visit(□□□□□□□□) the Facebook pages and websites of Fashion houses are					
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
5.	I can purchase) □□□□□) product from Karupalli’s Facebook page through bkash					
6.	I can pay) □□□□□□□□) without cash at Karupalli’s facebook page					

7.	I can pay)□□□□□□□□(without cash at other fashion houses facebook page and website that I mentioned above					
8.	Karupalli’s Facebook promotional) □□□□□□□□□□) activities influence me to buy products rather than other fashion houses					
9.	Karupalli’s Facebook advertisements) □□□□□□□□□□) influence) □□□□□□□□ □□□) me to buy products from them					
10.	Karupalli should turn (□□□□□□□□ □□□) their website in to an online purchase site to make purchase easy					

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